

D6.6 (M24) - Report on the outreach and training activities produced (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR

Project number: [322392](#)

Report prepared by: Terje Klemetsen

Contributors: [Terje Klemetsen](#) (TK), Helle T. Baalsrud (HB), [Espen Åberg](#) (EÅ), Sebastian Petters (SP), Nils P. Willassen (NPW)

Date: 1. April 2024

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11202427](#)

Keywords: Biodiversity training materials, outreach, networking, surveys, data management, ELIXIR Norway, EBP-Nor, molecular biodiversity, FAIR data principles, DIGIBANK INFRATECH application.

Context

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, through Work Package 6 (WP6) has been actively engaged in outreach and training activities to support the biodiversity research community in Norway. This report, Deliverable 6.6, documents the efforts made by WP6 to disseminate expertise and services through strategic outreach, training, and networking initiatives within the molecular biodiversity sector up until April 1 2024.

Outreach to the main biodiversity players in Norway has been a goal for WP6 as a way to support and empower the research community in molecular biodiversity by establishing a collaborative network among stakeholders. This activity also extends to the presentation of training material pertaining to ELIXIR services as a way to instruct and share expertise within collaborative projects as well as through conferences, webinars and talks to external researchers and students. WP6 also acts on behalf of ELIXIR Norway as a coordinator for potential grant applications within the research community in biodiversity. This report details the activities undertaken by WP6 and describes the continuation of knowledge sharing and networking.

Delivery

International networking

- Several members of WP6 have become members of the ELIXIR Europe [Biodiversity community](#) (former [focus group](#)) and are participating in meetings and activities along with the European nodes of ELIXIR.
 - The Biodiversity community is currently undergoing an implementation study having a duration of 2 years (2023-06 to 2025-06). TK is participating in work package 3 (Outreach, networking, and communications) of the implementation study to assist in tasks, milestones and deliverables. This included the virtual participation in the [ELIXIR Biodiversity Community F2F/hybrid meeting and Implementation Study meeting](#) held 13. September 2023.
 - WP6 will continue to partake in the ELIXIR Biodiversity community and its implementation study and exchange insights from activities as well as assist in tasks, milestones and deliverables.
- Talk held by TK at the [RoBioinfo conference](#) (2023-05-10) in Bucharest, Romania where the Marine Metagenomics Portal and its databases as well as the [Contextual Biodata Framework \(CBF\)](#) and the curation efforts of MarRef was presented:
 - Presentation slides ([10.5281/zenodo.10844507](#))
- Virtual talk held by HB at the [11th Hellenic Ecological Society Conference](#) (2023, 4-7 October), Greece, about the Norwegian Biodiversity Working Group started by ELIXIR Norway WP6 (ELIXIR3).

National networking

- Talk held by TK at the [BIOSCAN-NOReDNA conference](#) (2022-10-31), Trondheim, about ELIXIR Norway, data management and the CBF:
 - Presentation slides ([10.5281/zenodo.10844566](#))
- During the autumn of 2022 TK and NPW formulated an invitation to start the biodiversity working group (BWG) with the main actors making use of molecular biodiversity in Norway. The invitation was sent to representatives of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility Norway (GBIF), Norwegian Barcode of Life (NorBOL), Distributed System of Scientific Collections Norway (DiSSCo), Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), Earth BioGenome Project Norway (EBP-Nor), DNA Bank of the Natural History Museum of Oslo (NHMO), and Living Norway. The Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA) later joined the group in January 2024. The BWG's first meeting was held on 2022-11-26.
 - Since November 2022 the group has had regular meetings every last Thursday of the month. The meeting series has been organised by TK, HB, and SP.
 - [Running minutes](#) of the BWG.

- A survey was created by WP6 members, including TK, HB, SP with input and assistance from the BWG community. The survey topics ranged from data collection and data management and was distributed to several biodiversity communities in Norway. The survey was active in the period: 2024-02-16 to 2024-03-08 and held at [Nettskjema.no](https://nettskjema.no).
- WP6 will continue its activity concerning the BWG and hold meetings at regular monthly intervals during the lifetime of ELIXIR3. The BWG is a living network in which WP6 and the BWG seek to expand with additional relevant members from other initiatives in molecular biodiversity.
- Given the opportunity, WP6 will reach out to other networks via relevant conferences to present ELIXIR services and expertise for the biodiversity community.

Training events

- A virtual workshop was held by TK and NPW to introduce the use and functionalities of the EBP-Nor database system (<https://ebp-nor.sfb.uit.no>) for the sampling coordinators of EBP Norway. The workshop was held twice, 2022-03-16 and 2022-05-20, and organised as one hour hands-on sessions where samples could test inputting their own data or simulated data.
- Virtual talk by TK for the NTNU course [DLN BT8121](#) (hosted by [Digital Life Norway](#) on the 2022-10-06) about metadata sample handling and data management in the EBP-Norway project.
 - Presentation slides ([10.5281/zenodo.10844341](https://zenodo.org/record/10844341))
- Virtual talk by TK for the [Life Science RDM group](#) (2023-03-15) on data management in the EBP-Nor project and the storage of sample data using the EBP-Nor database system.
 - Presentation slides ([10.5281/zenodo.10844341](https://zenodo.org/record/10844341))
- Training material was created by TK in the form of a manual for the CBF interface. The manual describes how to use the interface and how contextual data can be added and linked to ontologies and sources. The manual was extended to support EBP-Nor samplers and users of the CBF interface, including the EBP-Nor database system use case. The first version of the manual was created 2022-06-07 while a revision was created 2023-09-15 which is available for samplers at the EBP-Nor database web site (databases.ebpnor.org).
 - Manual ([10.5281/zenodo.10848311](https://zenodo.org/record/10848311))
- WP6 will continue to update and produce relevant training materials for database services like the MAR databases, SalmoBase, LiceBase, EBP-Nor database (use case), and pertinent services delivered by ELIXIR Norway, like the brokering service

for biodiversity datasets, tools, as well as standards and best practices used in molecular biodiversity.

Coordination of grant applications

- In May 2023 ELIXIR Norway and WP6 was contacted by the Tromsø University Museum regarding the DIGIBANK (Digital Infrastructure for Gaining Infinite Biological and Natural History Knowledge) application. Since then, TK and EÅ have participated in 10 meetings between the lead partner and consortium members to coordinate the project application and ELIXIR's role and contribution. The DIGIBANK application is linked to the call [HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-01](#) where it has been given the application ID: SEP-211009675. The application was submitted by the lead partner Tromsø University Museum on 2024-03-12.
- WP6 will be open to coordinate future roles for ELIXIR in relevant grant applications to empower biodiversity initiatives with ELIXIR expertise.

Outcomes

- Researchers and students in several communities, including those related to EBP-Norway, have been informed and/or instructed in the data management process by using the EBP-Nor database system. This also includes the minimum set of sample data needed for deposition of sequence data in ENA and how this can be achieved through data brokering via the combined NeLS and EBP-Nor database system. As phase 1 of the EBP-Norway initiative is ending in July 2024, the role of WP6 will be to follow up with training materials for data management in the EBP-Nor database system for the next phase of EBP Norway.
- WP6 has established the BWG network and its meeting series to exchange information between different biodiversity communities engaged with molecular data in Norway. Communities working with genomics, barcoding, monitoring, ecology, and biobanking from diverse interest pockets of biodiversity research benefit by sharing experiences, news, needs, and understand gaps experienced in terms of infrastructure, financing and competence.
 - The BWG has already proven beneficial through the gap survey on data collection and management circulated in these networks and in satellite networks. All partners have been involved in shaping the survey and assessing the output. In a white paper describing the current situation of molecular biodiversity in Norway, the survey findings will be published in an open journal for the wider scientific community to understand what gaps there are in the Norwegian biodiversity landscape.

- In collaboration with the BWG, WP6 also seeks additional partners in relevant networks to improve communication with biodiversity stakeholders.
- Through several talks and lectures, external researchers and students have learned about ELIXIR Norway, the ELIXIR Biodiversity community, outputs of WP6, its services, tools, databases, and the BWG.
- ELIXIR's involvement and role in the DIGIBANK will benefit the consortium with competence and expertise towards data management and dissemination, given the project gets financing. The submitted application states ELIXIR's contribution through the Norwegian and German ELIXIR nodes are to assist the DIGIBANK data management plan, have a consultancy role in ensuring interoperability and FAIRness in the DIGIBANK data flows, as well as assisting in the dissemination of the project output into relevant repositories and services - particularly those under the ELIXIR umbrella.